

Imaging and therapeutic targeting of the tumor immune microenvironment with biologics

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ABSTRACT

The important role of tumor microenvironmental elements in determining tumor progression and metastasis has been firmly established. In particular, the presence and activity profile of tumor-infiltrating immune cells may be associated with the outcome of the disease and may predict responsiveness to (immuno)therapy. Indeed, while some immune cell types, such as macrophages, support cancer cell outgrowth and mediate therapy resistance, the presence of activated CD8⁺ T cells is usually indicative of a better prognosis. It is therefore of the utmost interest to obtain a full picture of the immune infiltrate in tumors, either as a prognostic test, as a way to stratify patients to maximize therapeutic success, or as therapy follow-up. Hence, the non-invasive imaging of these cells is highly warranted, with biologics being prime candidates to achieve this goal.

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Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Different formats of biologics for imaging and therapy in cancer	2
3. Biologics for the imaging and therapeutic targeting of myeloid cells in cancer	2
4. Biologics for the imaging and therapeutic targeting of tumor-associated macrophages	4
5. Biologics for the imaging of T cells in cancer	5
6. Biologics for the imaging of activated T cells in cancer	7
7. Biologics for the imaging of immune checkpoint molecules in cancer	8
8. A special case: Imaging of adoptively transferred T cells in cancer	9
9. Perspectives	10
Funding sources	11
Declaration of Competing Interest	11
References	11

1. Introduction

Cancer is a complex disease which displays a high variability in its etiology, presentation and development. Even the outcome for patients with the same histological tumor stage can largely diverge [1], highlighting the need to define tumor-related aspects that have

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an impact on the prognosis of the disease. In recent years, the influence of tumor-infiltrating immune cells on cancer progression [2] and treatment outcome has been heavily investigated [3,4], establishing their association with cancer prognosis [5]. While several immune cell types such as tumor-associated macrophages (TAM), tumor-associated neutrophils (TAN) and regulatory T cells (Treg) mostly associate with a worse prognosis, CD8⁺ cytotoxic T cells are often indicative of a better outcome [5,6]. Hence, methodologies to easily assess the immune composition of tumors are highly warranted.

In addition to their prognostic value, immune cells can also be harnessed to fight cancer. Indeed, several successful immune-based treatments have been developed, demonstrating durable responses across several cancer types. One of the best examples of such a breakthrough immunotherapy is represented by immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs), which block negative regulatory signaling and as such increase anti-tumor T-cell activity [7]. However, as is the case for several other cancer treatments, the response to ICIs is not uniform across cancer patients [8], highlighting the need for indicators which can predict and monitor the response to immunotherapies, leading to more personalized treatments. Besides the benefit for the patient, a better stratification of patients can also have a massive economic impact on the constantly increasing cost of cancer therapy [9].

To date, anti-tumor immunity in patients is estimated from tissue biopsies or blood biomarkers. However, these techniques are invasive, do not provide a complete picture of the TME and/or lack spatial information. As such, non-invasive imaging of immunoregulatory and cytotoxic immune cells has emerged as an interesting alternative strategy and has shown promising (pre)clinical results. Molecular imaging typically utilizes a targeting vehicle able to deliver the imaging agent to specific cells in the tumor microenvironment (TME). In the ideal scenario, the same vehicle could be formulated to deliver therapeutic compounds to those cells in the TME. Although other biologics have been used solely for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes, we provide here an overview of those biologics used to specifically target immune cells in solid tumors that have been employed as both diagnostic and therapeutic agents due to their amenability to engineering and conjugation. We believe that such image-guided therapy holds great promise in cancer treatment.

2. Different formats of biologics for imaging and therapy in cancer

The global biologics market size was USD 299.72 Billion in 2020 and is expected to reach USD 567.96 Billion in 2028, approximately 40% of which is accounted for by monoclonal antibodies (mAbs). Also in oncology, mAbs have been instrumental elements in targeted cancer therapy, recognizing antigens on cancer cells and sensitizing them for destruction, antigens on immune cells to enhance their anti-tumoral activity or antigens on other stromal cells to prevent their tumor-supporting role. Also in molecular imaging approaches, mAbs have been considered [10]. However, regardless of the success of mAbs as diagnostic and therapeutic agents, these molecules face some limitations. mAbs have large masses which are further elevated upon coupling to other molecules, strongly impacting the mAb's biodistribution and limiting their tumor penetration in comparison to smaller constructs [11,12,13]. Moreover, their long serum half-life complicates the establishment of a fast target-to-noise ratio (which is needed for same-day imaging with sufficient contrast) [14] and could induce toxicity due to a slow clearance rate, especially in the case of mAbs conjugated to toxic moieties such as radio-isotopes [15,16]. Other limitations in the use of mAbs as therapeutic moieties include high production costs,

high Fc-mediated aspecific binding, and the possible requirement of high doses to accomplish a therapeutic effect [17].

Therefore, smaller antigen-binding molecules were in demand. In first instance, mAbs have been size-reduced into antigen-binding, variable, and single-chain variable fragments, diabodies and minibodies, but these compounds still suffer from a relatively low clearance and extravasation rate [18]. A highly appealing alternative to mAbs and their derivatives, solving several of their issues, was provided by heavy chain-only Abs (HcAbs) that were discovered in species of the *camelidae* family [19]. In comparison to conventional antibodies, HcAbs are devoid of light chains rendering their variable domain monomeric, without compromising the affinity for the antigen. This discovery opened up the horizon to the generation of functional single variable domains from camelid HcAbs (V_HHs), or what came to be known as nanobodies (Nbs) [20]. Nbs are the smallest naturally occurring, antigen binding domains (~15 kDa), whose small size grants them an advantage over mAbs in penetrating tissues, including solid tumors, and reaching high target-to-noise ratios [13,21]. Moreover, their production cost is low, they are highly stable and soluble and recognize unconventional epitopes, which encouraged their use for various therapeutic and diagnostic purposes [22]. Finally, several small non-immunoglobulin protein scaffolds have been developed, including Affibodies, designed ankyrin repeat proteins (DARPs), anticalins and fibronectin type III (FN3, Adnectin), which are amenable to fast molecular imaging [14,23].

3. Biologics for the imaging and therapeutic targeting of myeloid cells in cancer

The immune composition of cancers is generally divided into lymphoid and myeloid cells, with the latter often being the most abundant, constituting up to 50% of the total tumor mass in some cancer types [24,25]. The myeloid infiltrate in tumors, typified by the expression of the integrin α M or CD11b, includes an array of different immune cell types such as macrophages, neutrophils, dendritic cells (DCs) and eosinophils. Several of those cell types are notorious for supporting tumor growth and metastasis and suppressing antitumor adaptive immune responses [26,27], implying that examining the infiltration of CD11b⁺ cells into tumors can be of importance and several tools have been developed for this purpose (Fig. 1 and Table 1). In addition, CD11b can be functionally involved in the protumoral activities of myeloid cells, as exemplified by the retarded tumor growth of melanoma and colon carcinoma tumors in *Cd11b*-deficient mice [28,29]. Yang *et al.* radiolabeled an anti-CD11b monoclonal antibody (mAb) with technetium-99 m (^{99m}Tc), and injected it in colon cancer-bearing mice. This enabled the visualization of colorectal nodules as small as 3 mm in diameter using single-photon emission computed tomography/computed tomography (SPECT/CT) imaging [30]. Along the same line, a different clone of anti-CD11b mAb, M1/70, was labelled with zirconium-89 (⁸⁹Zr) and successfully used to image myeloid cells in mice bearing an orthotopic syngeneic GL261 glioma, using positron emission tomography/CT (PET/CT) [31]. Of note, Cao *et al.* recently conjugated the M1/70 clone to copper-64 (⁶⁴Cu) (resulting in ⁶⁴Cu-DOTA-anti-CD11b) and used PET/CT to nicely visualize the difference between acute and chronic ear inflammation. During the acute phase, a marked increase in CD11b⁺ cell infiltration into the inflamed ear and a concomitant reduction in the bone marrow myeloid cell content was observed as compared to the chronic phase, reflecting an initial mobilization of myeloid cells from bone marrow to the inflammatory site followed by a compensatory regeneration of CD11b⁺-myeloid cells in the bone marrow [32]. Following this successful approach, the same authors utilized ⁶⁴Cu-labeled anti-CD11b

Fig. 1. Myeloid-targeted biologics for imaging and therapy. Overview of the different surface markers and respective cell types used for imaging and therapeutic targeting of myeloid cells. For each surface marker, the different biologics used for targeting are presented. APCs: antigen presenting cells; TAMs: tumor-associated macrophages.

mAb to monitor the kinetics of myeloid cells in the bone marrow of nude mice bearing human MDA-MB-435 melanoma xenografts following therapy with Abraxane, a nanoparticle albumin-bound paclitaxel which is known to deplete bone marrow cells [33]. Via this non-invasive imaging, the authors could confirm the depletion of bone marrow myeloid cell by Abraxane, but at the same time demonstrate that anti-CSF-1 mAbs potentially enhanced tolerance of bone marrow granulocytic myeloid cells to Abraxane, decreased cell migration, and suppressed the recruitment of myeloid cells to the tumor microenvironment [33].

Considering the various pro-tumoral functions of myeloid cells, several groups utilized the M1/70 anti-CD11b clone to therapeutically deplete myeloid cells in mice [34,35]. Injecting this antibody in immunodeficient mice bearing a human head and neck squamous cell carcinoma xenograft led to a significant enhancement of the tumor's response to radiation [35]. Mechanistically, the anti-CD11b mAbs inhibited the migration of bone marrow-derived myeloid cells toward chemotactic stimuli and consequently reduced the radiation-induced infiltration of myeloid cells into tumors [35]. Similarly, combining an anti-CD11b mAb with the chemotherapeutic agent paclitaxel in mice bearing orthotopic

PyMT breast adenocarcinoma tumors, led to a synergistic reduction in tumor growth [36].

Considering their advantages, Nbs were also employed to image and therapeutically target CD11b⁺ myeloid cells. Indeed, Rashidian *et al.* generated a fluorine-18 (¹⁸F)-labelled anti-CD11b Nb, named DC13, to successfully detect the infiltration of myeloid cells into murine B16F10 melanoma tumors [37]. In later studies, ⁸⁹Zr-anti-CD11b Nb DC13 was able to visualize the dynamics of CD11b⁺ cells in a colon carcinoma murine tumor model, MC38, during anti-PD-1 treatment, using PET [38]. Interestingly, shrinkage of tumors in responders correlated with an increase in the CD11b⁺ population in the center of the tumors, with transcriptomics demonstrating a pro-inflammatory phenotype of these myeloid cells [38]. Next, the possibility was explored to use the anti-CD11b Nb DC13 as a vaccine, due to its ability to deliver conjugated antigens to CD11b⁺ antigen-presenting cells (APC), including macrophages and DCs. DC13-tumor antigen conjugates could indeed elicit antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cells *in vivo* [39]. Moreover, the vaccination was efficient in both prophylactic and therapeutic settings, since mice immunized with DC13-tumor antigen were protected against a later tumor challenge, while injecting the con-

Table 1
Overview of biologics to image and target myeloid cells.

Target	Reactivity	Conjugate	Clone	Biological agent	Purpose	Discovery stage	reference
CD11b	Human	^{99m} Tc-anti-CD11b	EP1345Y	mAb	Imaging	Preclinical	[30]
	possibly* mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-anti-CD11b	M1/70	mAb	Imaging	Preclinical	[31,32,33]
	mouse	⁶⁴ Cu-anti-CD11b	M1/70	mAb	Therapy	Preclinical	[34,35,36]
	mouse	anti-CD11b ¹⁸ F-CD11b	DC13	Nb	Imaging	preclinical	[37,38]
MHC-II	mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-anti-CD11b	DC13	Nb	Therapy	preclinical	[39]
	mouse	E7 ₄₉₋₅₇ - anti-CD11b SIIN-anti-MHC-II	DC15	Nb	Therapy	preclinical	[46]
	mouse	M9-anti-MHC-II ¹⁸ F-anti-MHC-II	VHH7	Nb	Imaging	Preclinical	[37]
F4/80	mouse	¹⁸ F-anti-MHC-II	VHH7, DC8	Nb	Imaging	Preclinical	[40]
	mouse	¹¹¹ In-anti-F4/80	Cl:A3-1	mAb	Imaging	Preclinical	[52]
	mouse	anti-F4/80	Cl:A3-1	mAb	Therapy	Preclinical	[56]
	mouse	anti-F4/80	F4/80	mAb	Therapy	Preclinical	[53]
	mouse	anti-F4/80	HB-198	mAb	Therapy	Preclinical	[54,55]
MMR	mouse	DyLight680-anti-MMR IRDye700-anti-MMR Dylight755-anti-MMR I ¹²⁵ -anti-MMR	C068C2	mAb	Imaging	Preclinical	[68,69,70]
	mouse	^{99m} Tc-anti-MMR	Cl1	Nb	Imaging	Preclinical	[71]
	mouse	¹¹¹ In-anti-MMR	Cl1	Nb	Imaging	Preclinical	[76]
	mouse	¹⁷⁷ Lu-anti-MMR	Cl1	Nb	Therapy	Preclinical	[76]
	mouse	IMDQ-anti-MMR	Cl1	Nb	Therapy	Preclinical	[77]
	mouse	tSMAC-mWasabi-anti-MMR	Cl1	Nb	Therapy	Preclinical	[65]
	Human/ mouse	^{99m} Tc-anti-MMR ¹⁸ F-FB-anti-MMR	3.49, 14.4	Nb	Imaging	Preclinical	[64]
	mouse	^{99m} Tc-anti-SIRP α	Nb15	Nb	Imaging	Preclinical	[79]
	human	anti-SIRP α	1H9	mAb	Therapy	Preclinical	[82]
	mouse human	anti-SIRP α anti-SIRP α	MY-1 KWAR23	mAb mAb	Therapy Therapy	Preclinical Preclinical	[83,84] [85]

*: on the provider's website, it is stated that the mAb reactivity is verified against human CD11b, but contradicting results were obtained against mouse CD11b. Therefore, the provider only listed it as reactive with human CD11b.

jugate in mice with established tumors led to tumor regression and enhanced survival [39].

APCs also include B cells, which are lymphoid cells and would, hence, be missed with a CD11b-directed approach. However, a commonality between all APCs is their expression of major histocompatibility complex (MHC)-II molecules, inspiring the use of anti-MHC-II targeting moieties. Two different clones of ¹⁸F-conjugated anti-MHC-II Nbs were used for PET imaging in order to track the infiltration of MHC-II⁺ cells into various mouse tumors [37,40]. Of note, an anti-human MHC-II Nb has been generated and successfully used for whole-body PET imaging in a humanized graft-versus-host disease model [41], suggesting that it could also be of use for imaging in a cancer context. In addition, an anti-MHC-II Nb [42], but also mAb [43,44,45], have been used to target drugs to malignant B cell lymphomas. In this context, the polymorphic nature of MHC-II adds an extra layer of complexity to the generation of pan-human MHC-II-binding biologics. Finally, anti-MHC-II Nb/tumor neoantigen conjugates were employed to deliver peptide epitopes to APCs, resulting in the induction of antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cell responses *in vitro* and *in vivo* [46]. However, there was no prophylactic nor therapeutic benefit of injecting these Nb conjugates, possibly due to the low immunogenicity of the employed peptides, suggesting that a more immunogenic tumor model known to escape immune recognition through low antigen presentation might unleash the potential of this approach.

4. Biologics for the imaging and therapeutic targeting of tumor-associated macrophages

Though the imaging and targeting of all CD11b⁺ myeloid cells in the TME has proven its use, it lacks the granularity to discriminate between tumor-promoting and tumor-destructive myeloid cell

populations. In both human and mouse tumors, macrophages are amongst the most prominent myeloid cell types infiltrating the TME [47] and their high abundance is linked to a worse prognosis in the majority of cancer types [48]. Moreover, TAMs are implicated in the development of resistance to various cancer therapies, including ICIs [49,50], overall suggesting that a pretreatment assessment of TAM presence in tumors could have a prognostic value for therapy success. Several biologics have been developed to image and target TAMs (Table 1). For instance, F4/80 is a G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) which has been used for years as a murine macrophage marker [51], so several anti-F4/80 mAbs have been employed for macrophage imaging and targeted therapy. An indium-111 (¹¹¹In)-labeled anti-F4/80 mAb was used to visualize TAMs with SPECT/CT after injecting the conjugate in SCID/Beige mice bearing orthotopic MDA-MB-231 human breast cancer xenografts. The scans showed the ability of the conjugate to bind TAMs, but also macrophages in the liver and spleen which act as sinks [52]. The authors argued that such an approach could be useful to monitor TAM responses to novel or existing therapies, since the tracer was still detectable 72 h post its injection, in comparison to only 3 h for smaller constructs such as Nbs. However, longer circulation times decrease the contrast of the images, and may be accompanied by toxic side effects of the radioisotope. A non-depleting, unconjugated, antagonistic anti-F4/80 mAb was used by Zhang *et al.* to unravel the role of F4/80, and by extension TAMs, in anti-PD-L1 therapy of B16-OVA murine melanoma tumors. Interestingly, the therapeutic effect of anti-PD-L1 therapy was abrogated upon co-treatment with the anti-F4/80 mAb, which lowered the expression of MHC-I, MHC-II, CD80, and CD86 on TAMs, likely leading to an impairment of antigen presentation and co-stimulation [53]. A depleting anti-F4/80 mAb has also been used to examine the role of TAMs, especially in mesothelioma

tumors in elderly mice [54,55]. TAM depletion caused a slower tumor growth and, when combined with IL-2/anti-CD40 immunotherapy, increased the anti-tumor T-cell activity resulting in regression of 78% of tumors. Moreover, depletion of TAMs in this setting protected mice from cachexia, which is normally induced in elderly mice by IL-2/anti-CD40 combination therapy [55]. Chamberlin *et al.* have also used a depleting anti-F4/80 mAb to explore the relationship between macrophages, obesity, and preneoplastic changes. Interestingly, the depletion of macrophages exacerbated the appearance of breast epithelial cells with DNA damage in obese mice, demonstrating an unanticipated protective role of macrophages against obesity-induced preneoplastic breast lesions [56]. Altogether, these data identify F4/80 as a suitable marker for the imaging and depletion of macrophages in mice, but also as a mediator of TAM's antigen presenting capacity. Unfortunately, the direct translation of these results to a human setting is not possible considering that the human ortholog of F4/80, the epidermal growth factor (EGF)-like module containing mucin-like hormone receptor 1 (EMR1), does not mirror the murine F4/80 expression pattern. In fact, EMR1 is not expressed by mononuclear phagocytic cells such as monocytes, macrophages, and DCs, but is specifically expressed on human eosinophils [57].

In recent years, it has become clear that the TAM population in tumors is heterogeneous, often demonstrating a co-existence of cells with an anti- or pro-tumoral phenotype depending on the environmental signals and localization within the tumor [58,59,60,61,62,63,64]. Single cell transcriptomics has taken this concept even a step further, uncovering multiple TAM populations with specialized functions within the TME [65]. Therefore, when evaluating TAM infiltration into tumors, special emphasis should be devoted to their phenotype. For instance, patients with a higher anti-tumoral/pro-tumoral TAM ratio exhibited a better prognosis in several cancer types [66], highlighting the importance of including macrophage profiling in clinical evaluation and treatment decisions. Several markers have been linked to a pro-tumoral TAM phenotype, of which the macrophage mannose receptor (MMR) or CD206 arguably has been best studied [67]. Indeed, MMR^{high} TAMs were shown to locate in hypoxic tumor areas and to possess T-cell suppressive and pro-angiogenic potential [62,63]. Pro-tumoral TAMs in 4T1 mammary carcinoma tumors have been visualized with an anti-MMR mAb labeled with near-infrared (NIR) dyes such as dylight680, dye IRDye700 and Dylight755 for NIR fluorescence (NIRF) imaging [68,69,70] or with iodine-125 (I [125]) for SPECT/CT imaging [69,70]. Moreover, the IRDye700-labelled anti-MMR mAb was used for photoimmunotherapy (PIT) as the dye can be activated by focal NIR light irradiation, leading to necrotic cell death and subsequently slower tumor growth and decreased lung metastasis [69]. In a follow-up study, the anti-MMR mAb-based NIRF and SPECT/CT imaging was used for the early prediction of tumor relapse after chemotherapy [70]. Also Nbs have been employed to image and target protumoral TAMs, with both mouse-specific and mouse/human cross-reactive anti-MMR Nbs targeting pro-tumoral MMR^{high} TAMs *in vitro* and *in vivo* [71,72,73,74,75,76,77]. Movahedi *et al.* [71] and Blykers *et al.* [72] used anti-MMR Nbs to visualize MMR^{high} TAMs in various murine tumor models using SPECT and PET imaging, respectively. Based on these results, a phase I/IIa clinical trial has been initiated to evaluate the tolerability and safety of Ga⁶⁸-labelled anti-MMR Nb for PET/CT scanning in cancer patients with melanoma, breast and head and neck cancer (NCT04168528). Furthermore, in a phase II clinical trial, non-operable solid cancer patients will be imaged with ⁶⁸Ga-anti-MMR Nb pre- and post-treatment, including ICIs (NCT04758650), to assess the prognostic value of MMR-imaging. For therapy, Bolli *et al.* labeled anti-MMR Nbs with lutetium-177 (¹⁷⁷Lu), a medium-energy β -emitter used for radiotherapy and proved its efficacy in halting tumor growth

of the TS/A murine mammary carcinoma model, a strategy that was termed stromal-targeted radioimmunotherapy or STRIT [76]. In this model, STRIT surpassed the therapeutic efficacy of established cancer therapies such as chemotherapy and ICI [76]. Moreover, a conjugate of anti-MMR Nb with imidazoquinoline (IMDQ), a toll-like receptor (TLR)7/8 agonist, was able to repolarize TAMs towards a pro-inflammatory phenotype and to increase effector T-cell responses, leading to reduced lung carcinoma growth [77]. One caveat of using anti-MMR Nbs, is the high antigenic sink in the liver, which is mainly due to MMR-expression by liver sinusoidal endothelial cells [78]. An elegant strategy to circumvent this problem, at least in mice, is to treat the animals with a molar excess of unlabeled bivalent anti-MMR Nbs, which rapidly occupy the extra-tumoral binding sites in the liver but still allow labeled monovalent anti-MMR to enter the tumor and bind MMR^{high} TAMs [76,77].

Most recently, CITE-sequencing efforts revealed signal regulatory protein alpha (SIRP α) as a protein prominently expressed at the surface of microglia- and monocyte-derived TAMs in human and mouse glioblastoma tumors [79]. Interestingly, a ^{99m}Tc-labeled anti-SIRP α Nb showed a clear tumor uptake in comparison to a control non-targeting Nb, but also accumulated in peripheral organs such as spleen and liver [79]. A bivalent construct of this Nb exhibited an increased accumulation in spleen and liver, but did not penetrate the tumor. These data again highlight the advantage of monovalent Nbs for intratumoral uptake and provide a proof-of-concept for using anti-SIRP α nanobodies to non-invasively image myeloid cells in intracranial glioblastoma tumors with high signal-to-noise ratios, even without blood-brain barrier permeabilization. The interaction of SIRP α with its ligand, CD47, leads to inhibition of phagocytosis [80]. In fact, one of the established mechanisms of immune evasion by cancer cells is the upregulation of the CD47 "don't-eat-me" signal [81]. Therefore, a lot of effort has been devoted to the modulation of the SIRP α /CD47 axis as cancer therapy. Even though a blocking anti-CD47 IgG4 was evaluated in a phase I clinical trial (NCT02678338) and regarded as well tolerated, considerable portions of patients suffered from anemia and hemagglutination. These side effects are the result of the mAb binding to CD47 expressed by red blood cells (RBCs), highlighting the need for a better alternative. Liu *et al.* recently showed that in comparison to an anti-CD47 mAb, anti-SIRP α mAbs suffered less from an antigen sink effect due to the limited tissue expression of SIRP α . They also carried out toxicological studies in non-human primates to show that the anti-SIRP α mAb is well tolerated with no treatment-related adverse effects. Moreover, the therapeutic capacity of the anti-SIRP α mAb was demonstrated pre-clinically as it caused a slower growth of mouse B16F10 melanoma tumors as a monotherapy, with even a superior therapeutic effect when combined with anti-PD-L1 ICI [82]. Several other groups have also shown the efficacy of blocking anti-SIRP α mAbs in cancer treatment [83,84,85], highlighting it as an interesting emerging ICI.

5. Biologics for the imaging of T cells in cancer

As T cells play a pivotal role in the anti-tumor immune response, T-cell-based immunotherapies have been a major focus in the field of cancer immunotherapy [86]. The main goal of these immunotherapies is to recruit and/or activate cytotoxic T cells inside the tumor [86]. Overall, these therapies can be subdivided based on their mechanism of action, namely the blockade of T-cell inhibitory signals on naturally occurring anti-tumor T cells, increasing the availability of naturally occurring T cells via T-cell engagers, or artificially boosting the presence of anti-tumor T cells via the adoptive transfer of natural or modified T cells (e.g. CAR T-cells). Since all these approaches are in the clinic, and are making

Fig. 2. T cell targeting biological imaging agents. Overview of the different surface markers used for imaging of different T cell populations. For each surface marker, the different radiolabeled biologics targeting these markers are presented.

their way as first line treatments for multiple indications, it becomes important to non-invasively image T cells and T-cell activity for prognosis and as therapy follow-up (Fig. 2).

One approach to visualize and quantify the infiltration and distribution of T cells in tumors (Table 2) is via targeting the T-cell surface protein CD3. Using ^{89}Zr -labeled anti-mouse CD3 mAbs, antibody accumulation was seen in the spleen, thymus, lymph nodes and bone marrow of healthy mice and in the TME of syngeneic bladder tumor-bearing mice via PET/CT scanning and *ex vivo* biodistribution [87]. In an additional study, the response to anti-CTLA-4 therapy in CT26 colorectal carcinoma tumor-bearing mice was predicted via quantification of T-cell infiltration using the same ^{89}Zr -labeled anti-CD3 mAb [99]. Mice showing a high tumor-to-blood uptake of this mAb developed significantly smaller tumors over time, illustrating the potential of predicting the strength of an anti-tumor immune response by visualizing tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes.

However, the imaging of CD3⁺ cells does not differentiate between different T-cell populations. For instance, the specific tracking of (tumor-infiltrating) CD8⁺ cytotoxic T cells is of a greater interest as these cells are one of the key effector cells mediating the success of immunotherapy [88]. In 2014, Tavaré *et al.* described the generation of two anti-mouse CD8 minibodies (antibody fragment consisting of the VL, VH and CH3 domain) that, upon ^{64}Cu -labeling, acquired high contrast PET-images 4 h post injection [89] and showed specific *in vivo* uptake in the spleen and lymph nodes of healthy mice. Based on these minibodies, a ^{89}Zr -labeled anti-mouse CD8 cys-diabody (consisting of covalently dimerized ScFv fragments) was generated that exhibited increased tumor uptake

in CT26 tumor-bearing mice responding to anti-PD-L1 therapy as compared to non-responders [90]. In follow-up studies, the same cys-diabody could visualize changes in tumor CD8⁺ T cell infiltration during anti-PD-1 and CpG immunotherapy in a breast cancer model [91], as well as during oncolytic virus therapy in an orthotopic glioma model [92]. Recently, a ^{89}Zr -labeled minibody targeting human CD8 (^{89}Zr -labeled IAB22M2C) was clinically tested in a first-in-human prospective single dose study [93], showing high uptake in the tumor, spleen, kidney and liver of melanoma, lung and hepatocellular carcinoma patients. This tracer will now be evaluated in a Phase IIA multi-dose clinical trial in patients with metastatic solid tumors before and after immunotherapy treatment (NCT03802123). Other groups have been investigating the use of Nbs for the non-invasive imaging of CD8⁺ T cells. In 2017, Rashidian *et al.* generated a Nb targeting mouse CD8, whose half-life time and hydrophilicity was increased by the addition of a polyethylene glycol (PEG) moiety. This was potentially the reason for the enhanced target-to-background signal and reduced kidney uptake seen upon ^{89}Zr -labeling [94] compared to a non-PEGylated version of this Nb. Using this ^{89}Zr -labeled PEGylated Nb, the responsiveness of mouse B16 melanoma tumors to anti-CTLA-4 treatment could be predicted by looking at a homogenous CD8⁺ T cell intra-tumoral distribution. In a later study, responders and non-responders to anti-PD-1 treatment in a colorectal cancer model could be differentiated by imaging the CD8⁺ T-cell infiltration. Overall, responders showed a good CD8⁺ T cell tumor penetration, while non-responders showed accumulation of the CD8⁺ T cells in the tumor periphery [38]. One study reported the generation of a human CD8-targeting Nb for non-invasive imaging pur-

Table 2
overview of different nuclear imaging T cell-tracers.

Target	Reactivity	Molecule	Biological agent	Discovery stage	reference
CD3	mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-DFO-antiCD3 (clones BE0002 and 17A2)	mAb	Preclinical	[87,100]
CD8	Mouse	⁶⁴ Cu-NOTA-2.43 Mb	Minibody	Preclinical	[89]
		⁴ Cu-NOTA-YTS169 Mb			
	Mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-malDFO-169 cDb	Cys-diabody	Preclinical	[90]
	Mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-PEGylated VHH-X118	Nanobody	Preclinical	[38,94]
	Human	⁸⁹ Zr-IAB22M2C	Minibody	Clinical	[93]
					NCT03802123
	Human	⁶⁸ Ga-NOTA-SNA006	Nanobody	Preclinical	[95]
CD4	Mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-malDFO-GK1.5 cDb	Cys-diabody	Preclinical	[96]
TCR	Mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-Df-aTCRmu-F(ab') ₂	F(ab') ₂ fragment	Preclinical	[98,99]
ICOS	Mouse	⁹⁰ Zr-DFO-ICOS mAb (clone: 7E.17G9)	mAb	Preclinical	[101]
OX40	Mouse	⁶⁴ Cu-DOTA-AbOX40 (clone OX86)	mAb	Preclinical	[102]
IL-2R	human	[¹⁸ F]FB-IL-2	Interleukin	Clinical	[103,104]
					NCT02478099, NCT03304223, NCT04163094, NCT02922283
Granzyme B	Mouse	⁶⁸ Ga-NOTA-GZP	Peptide	Preclinical	[105]
IFN-γ	Mouse	⁸⁹ Zr-anti-IFN-γ (clone AN-18)	mAb	Preclinical	[106]
CTLA-4	Mouse	⁶⁴ Cu-DOTA-anti-CTLA-4 mAb	mAb	Preclinical	[107]
	Mouse	¹⁸ F-H11	Nanobody	Preclinical	[108]
		⁸⁹ Zr -H11-PEG20			
	Human	⁶⁴ Cu-NOTA-ipilimumab	mAb	Preclinical	[109]
	Human	⁶⁴ Cu-NOTA-ipilimumab-F(ab') ₂	F(ab') ₂ fragment	Preclinical	[109]
	Human	⁸⁹ Zr- ipilimumab	mAb	Clinical	NCT03313323
PD-1	Mouse	⁶⁴ Cu-DOTA-anti-mouse-PD-1 mAb (clone J43.1)	mAb	Preclinical	[110]
	Mouse	⁶⁴ Cu-NOTA-PD-1 mAb (clone RMP1-14)	mAb	Preclinical	[111]
	Human	⁶⁴ Cu pembrolizumab	mAb	Preclinical	[112]
	Human	⁸⁹ Zr-pembrolizumab	mAb	Clinical	[113,114,115,116]
	Human	⁸⁹ Zr-nivolumab	mAb	Clinical	[117,118]
LAG-3	Mouse	^{99m} Tc-labeled nanobody 3132	Nanobody	Preclinical	[119,120]
TIGIT	Mouse	⁶⁴ Cu-TIGIT mAb	mAb	Preclinical	[121]
		⁸⁹ Zr-TIGIT mAb (Clone 1G9)			

poses [95]. While good *in vitro* and *in vivo* Nb affinity and specificity were shown, the potential of this tracer to predict immunotherapy responsiveness in patients remains to be investigated.

Besides CD8⁺ T cells, efforts have been made to non-invasively image mouse CD4⁺ cells, using a ⁸⁹Zr-labeled CD4-targeting cys-diabody in naïve mice that showed a high uptake in lymphoid organs 20 h post injection [96]. However, a differentiation between different CD4⁺ cell populations (pro-inflammatory Th1 cells, immunosuppressive Tregs and CD4⁺ DCs) is not possible, hampering the use of a single CD4-targeting probe for predicting therapy responsiveness.

Finally, T cell receptors (TCRs) have been employed as targets for the non-invasive imaging of adoptive T cell transfer immunotherapies, since binding to these receptors results in a high accumulation of the tracer inside the cells due to constant receptor internalization [97]. TCR-transgenic human memory CD8⁺ T cells were as such visualized *in vivo* with a ⁸⁹Zr-labeled F(ab')₂ fragment targeting the mouse TCR-β domain. This F(ab')₂ fragment showed a high specificity and affinity towards the engineered T cells and allowed a sensitive estimation of T-cell engraftment and tumor infiltration in an acute myeloid sarcoma model [98,99].

Overall, these data demonstrate that the *in vivo* imaging of T cells or T-cell populations allows to visualize, prognose or even predict immunotherapy responses. To this end, different biological scaffolds such as mAbs, F(ab')₂ fragments, diabodies, minibodies and Nbs have been developed of which some are being translated towards the clinic (Table 2).

6. Biologics for the imaging of activated T cells in cancer

While the visualization of tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) allows the prediction of immunotherapy responses, it does not dif-

ferentiate between non-activated (naïve, exhausted or anergic) and activated T cells, the latter obviously being the major contributors to anti-tumor immunity. Therefore, tracking of activated T cells is of great interest. In this context, the upregulation of surface activation markers such as ICOS, OX40, IL-2 receptor alpha chain (CD25) or the expression of secreted markers such as Granzyme B and IFN-γ can be used as targets for the non-invasive imaging of activated T cells.

The co-stimulatory receptor ICOS is expressed on both activated CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells [122]. Using a ⁸⁹Zr-labeled mAb targeting mouse ICOS, activated T cells could be visualized in a Lewis lung carcinoma model [101]. Moreover, tumor responsiveness to anti-PD-1 therapy, STING therapy or a combination therapy was assessed via the non-invasive imaging of ICOS⁺ T cells. Anti-PD-1 therapy only showed a modest therapeutic effect, which was confirmed by the lack of ICOS⁺ T-cell infiltration in the tumor. In contrast, STING therapy or anti-PD-1/STING combination therapy resulted in an increased tumor growth delay, which was paralleled by a significant increase of ICOS⁺ T cells inside the tumor. Along the same line, a ⁶⁴Cu-labeled anti-mouse OX40 mAb could be used for the visualization of activated T cells and could predict the immune response to CpG *in situ* vaccination in A20 lymphoma tumor-bearing mice [102].

An alternative to the use of mAbs for the imaging of immune receptors, is the use of labeled ligands for these receptors. As an example of this principle, the cytokine IL-2 has been used for the non-invasive imaging of high affinity IL-2 receptor (IL-2Rαβγ)-expressing activated T cells [123]. The infiltration of activated T lymphocytes in HPV antigen-carrying murine tumors, upon local radiation and/or vaccination, was determined using ¹⁸F-labeled IL-2 [103]. Local radiation resulted in a significantly enhanced tracer uptake inside the tumor compared to untreated animals. Moreover, IL-2 tracer uptake further increased 2.7 fold in animals

receiving both radiation and vaccination compared to animals receiving only radiation therapy. Furthermore, enhanced tumor infiltration of these activated T cells was driven by CXCR4-mediated chemotaxis as treatment with the CXCR4 antagonist AMD3100 dampened T cell tumor infiltration. This PET tracer is currently evaluated in multiple clinical trials (NCT02478099, NCT03304223, NCT04163094 and NCT02922283), including in metastatic melanoma patients during ICI therapy [124]. While PET imaging with ^{18}F -labeled IL-2 was proven to be safe and feasible in this trial, no ICI treatment-related ^{18}F -IL-2 signal was observed in this small patient group, which could be either due to insufficient activated T-cell infiltration or insufficient sensitivity of the imaging technique. Likewise, another pilot study investigated the potential of $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ -labeled IL-2 to visualize activated T cells in metastatic melanoma patients on pembrolizumab (anti-PD-1) or ipilimumab (anti-CTLA-4) treatment [104]. While tracer accumulation was seen in most lesions, some metastases demonstrated an enhanced uptake while other metastases showed a decreased uptake after ICI therapy. Moreover, one out of five patients reported to have grade 1 pruritus and grade 1 pain due to tracer injection. Further clinical trials will give more insight in the potential of this tracer, as these current trials show mixed results.

Also secreted molecules have been explored as markers to visualize activated T cells. Granzyme B is a serine protease that is released by activated CD8⁺ T cells and NK cells [125]. A ^{68}Ga -labeled peptide, serving as preferred granzyme B substrate, was able to differentiate responders and non-responders during anti-PD-1 monotherapy or anti-PD-1/CTLA-4 combination therapy in CT26 tumor-bearing mice [105]. Moreover, the clinical potential of this peptide tracer was shown by its ability to distinguish responders and non-responders via staining of biopsies from melanoma patients treated with nivolumab or pembrolizumab (both anti-PD-1). IFN- γ is a cytokine that is primarily produced by activated CD8⁺ T cells, Th1 cells, NK and NKT cells [126]. Elevated IFN- γ levels were detected via PET imaging using a ^{89}Zr -labeled anti-mouse IFN- γ mAb in orthotopic neu⁺ mammary and spontaneous salivary tumor models upon HER2/neu DNA vaccination. Interestingly, this enhanced tracer uptake was not seen anymore upon T-cell exhaustion, demonstrating its specificity for activated T cells.

In conclusion, promising preclinical results in the visualization of activated T cells have been obtained in the last years. However, it remains to be seen if imaging of activated T cells are clinically relevant as the first clinical trials have not yielded clear results. To this end, other (T-cell) activation markers such as 4-1BB and CD69 could prove to be interesting alternatives. Recently, a CD69-targeting affibody has been developed that could be used for non-invasive imaging purposes during immunotherapy treatment [127].

7. Biologics for the imaging of immune checkpoint molecules in cancer

Immune checkpoint inhibitor treatment has resulted in promising clinical outcomes in different cancer types. However, differences in therapy effectiveness between patients has been observed. Therefore, a non-invasive imaging approach whereby patients are selected based on the presence of certain biomarkers, often the immune checkpoints themselves, at the beginning or during immune checkpoint inhibitor treatment could aid in selecting more personalized treatments. Therefore, extensive (pre)clinical research has been performed on the imaging of multiple immune checkpoints (CTLA-4, PD-1, PD-L1, LAG-3, TIGIT) during immunotherapy, using biologics.

CTLA-4 is expressed upon activation of T cells and is constitutively expressed by Tregs. In a first preclinical study, imaging of CTLA-4-expressing cells was performed in CT26 colorectal carcinoma tumor-bearing mice using a ^{64}Cu -labeled mouse anti-CTLA-4 mAb. In this model, a small but significant uptake of the tracer was seen in the tumor as compared to the IgG control. Imaging of CTLA-4-expressing cells in B16 melanoma tumor-bearing mice was also shown via a ^{18}F - and ^{89}Zr -labeled anti-mouse CTLA-4 Nb. In another study, ipilimumab (anti-CTLA-4 mAb) and an ipilimumab-F(ab')₂ fragment were radiolabeled with ^{64}Cu and were able to visualize activated T cells in salivary glands of human PBMC-engrafted NOD-SCID mice [109]. Currently, a clinical trial (NCT03313323) is recruiting ipilimumab-treated metastatic melanoma patients to determine the uptake and biodistribution of ^{89}Zr -labeled ipilimumab and the potential correlation with therapy responsiveness and toxicity.

PD-L1 can be expressed on immune cells and cancer cells and inhibits T-cell function via interaction with PD-1, which is mostly expressed on T cells. In the case of PD-L1, immunohistochemical staining of biopsies, with all their shortcomings (invasive procedure, only providing information on a limited piece of tissue), is currently performed to determine PD-L1 expression and to decide on the eligibility of patients for anti-PD-L1 therapy [128]. Non-invasive imaging of PD-L1 could overcome these shortcomings and has been extensively investigated in (pre)clinical settings using different biological formats including mAbs, Nbs, affibodies, adnectins and probodies. Overall, both preclinical and clinical studies have yielded positive results, which has resulted in multiple clinical trials to further investigate the potential of non-invasive PD-L1, as amply described in other reviews [129,130,131].

PD-1 expression can also serve as a diagnostic marker for anti-PD-1 therapy and has resulted in multiple (pre)clinical studies that have visualized PD-1 expression. In two independent studies, murine PD-1 expression was determined in B16 tumor-bearing mice via PET imaging using ^{64}Cu -labeled anti-PD-1 mAbs. In both studies, high uptake in the tumor, spleen, kidney, liver and blood was seen 24 to 48 h post injection. Human PD-1 expression in humanized mice has also been imaged via radiolabeled pembrolizumab or nivolumab. In the case of pembrolizumab, NSG mice or melanoma tumor-bearing NOD-SCID mice, both engrafted with human PBMCs, were injected with the ^{89}Zr - or ^{64}Cu -labeled mAb. In these studies, specific uptake in the salivary glands (in the case of naïve mice) or tumor (in the case of tumor-bearing mice) was observed compared to non-PBMC engrafted mice. Another study performed similar experiments using ^{89}Zr -labeled nivolumab in non-small-cell lung carcinoma-tumor-bearing NOD-SCID mice that were engrafted with human PBMCs [117] with very comparable results, i.e. high tracer uptake in the tumor, spleen and salivary glands of engrafted mice. Following these promising preclinical results, PD-1 expression was determined in advanced non-small cell lung carcinoma patients using ^{89}Zr -labeled nivolumab [118]. In this study, higher tracer uptake was correlated with the presence of PD-1-positive tumor-infiltrating immune cells. Moreover, increased tracer uptake was seen in responders to anti-PD-1 therapy, indicating that this tracer could potentially be used for predicting anti-PD-1 therapy response. In addition, ^{89}Zr -labeled pembrolizumab has been tested in metastatic melanoma and non-small cell lung carcinoma patients in two independent clinical trials [115,116], demonstrating its overall safety with only one patient experiencing grade 3 myalgia. Both studies observed higher (although not significant) uptake in tumor lesions of anti-PD-1 therapy-responding patients.

LAG-3 is expressed on activated T cells, Tregs, NK cells, DCs and B cells [132], and its triggering results in a downregulation of anti-tumor T-cell function [133,134,135], classifying it as a bona fide immune checkpoint molecule. As such, LAG-3 blockade holds promise for cancer therapy, resulting in several clinical trials with

diverse LAG-3 blocking moieties. Consequently, LAG-3 imaging is gaining interest. In 2019, the generation of multiple mouse LAG-3-targeting Nbs was reported by Lecocq *et al* [119], with the ^{99m}Tc -labeled versions of these Nbs showing a high uptake in mice bearing LAG-3-overexpressing lung epithelial xenograft tumors 1 h post injection. In a follow-up study, the ^{99m}Tc -labeled lead LAG-3-targeting Nb was used to evaluate LAG-3 expression in different tumor models (MC38, MO4 and TC-1) [120], demonstrating LAG-3 upregulation on tumor-infiltrating T cells upon anti-PD-1 treatment of MC38 tumors via SPECT/CT. Overall, this shows the potential of imaging (changes in) LAG-3 as a possible aid in predicting therapy outcome.

Finally, TIGIT is another immune checkpoint molecule that is expressed on T and NK cells, whose blockade is currently investigated as monotherapy for cancer or in combination with other immune checkpoint blockade therapies [136,137,121]. TIGIT expression is generally high, but variable across solid tumor types, likely necessitating patient stratification to ensure the most beneficial therapeutic outcome [121]. To this end, a ^{64}Cu - and ^{89}Zr -labeled anti-mouse TIGIT mAb was generated for non-invasive PET imaging, both showing a specific accumulation in TIGIT-expressing Hela xenografts at 48 or 72 h post injection. Moreover, uptake of the ^{89}Zr -labeled anti-mouse TIGIT mAb was observed in mouse melanoma tumors, illustrating the feasibility of imaging TIGIT-expressing cells in the TME. Next steps should now be the development of anti-human TIGIT tracers and evaluating their use during immunotherapy treatments.

Taken together, the imaging of immune checkpoint molecules in the TME has shown great promise and has resulted in multiple tracers being investigated in clinical trials for patient stratification and therapy follow-up.

8. A special case: Imaging of adoptively transferred T cells in cancer

Adoptive T-cell therapy involves the intravenous transfer of tumor-resident or engineered peripheral T lymphocytes into the cancer patient to induce an anti-tumor response [138,139]. Similar to immune checkpoint blockade, these therapies have shown outstanding results but, again, only in a subset of patients [140]. The effectiveness of these therapies partially depends on the distribution, longevity, activation and overall survival of these (engineered) T cells [141,142,143]. Current methods to assess these aspects include flow cytometry, detection of cytokines and digital PCR [144,145,146]. However, PET imaging of these T cells could be more useful to predict the effectivity of the therapy. To this end, *in vivo* tracking of (engineered) T cells makes use of two distinct methods: direct or *ex vivo* labeling (whereby the imaging agent is loaded into the cells) or indirect or *in vivo* labeling (via the expression of reporter genes) (Fig. 3).

During direct labelling, T cells are isolated and incubated *ex vivo* with a contrast agent prior to being introduced into the patient. Direct labeling of T cells can be achieved through passive diffusion or by binding of the labeling agent to the cell membrane. Direct labeling protocols are quite straightforward, but the *ex vivo* labeling of T cells [147,148] for imaging also holds some disadvantages. First, the imaging window is time-limited as efflux of the agent can happen over time. In addition, *in vivo* efflux and retention of free radionuclide in the bone marrow is a concern. Second, the radioactive signal is diluted over time as cells are expanding *in vivo*, further limiting the imaging window. As such, labeling efficiencies and the amount of radioactivity should be high enough. Finally, direct labeling of the cells can result in certain forms of radio- or chemical toxicity and should be closely monitored.

Direct labeling via passive diffusion is routinely performed using chelators such as 8-hydroxy-quinoline (oxine), hexamethylpropyleneamine (HMPAO) or pyruvaldehyde-bis(N^4 -methylthiosemicarbazone (PTSM) which carry radioisotopes across the cell membrane [147]. In addition, several isotopes have been used, such as ^{111}In , ^{99m}Tc (in the case of SPECT/CT imaging), ^{64}Cu or ^{89}Zr (in the case of PET/CT imaging) [147]. PET imaging is more sensitive and quantitative compared to SPECT [149]. However, in the case of ^{64}Cu -labeling, a rapid efflux of ^{64}Cu -PTSM complexes was observed, resulting in a high liver uptake and jeopardizing the clinical translation of these complexes. Conversely, ^{89}Zr has a longer half-life allowing medium-to-long term cell tracking, making it a potential candidate for clinical direct cell labeling. In one study, *ex vivo* activated ^{89}Zr -oxine-labeled cytotoxic T cells were injected in melanoma tumor-bearing mice [150]. Using PET/CT imaging, the intratumoral accumulation of these T cells could be visualized and resulted in tumor regression. In another study, human anti-IL-13R α 2 CAR T cells, targeting human glioblastoma cells, were efficiently radiolabeled with ^{89}Zr -oxine with more than 60% of the cells retaining the radiolabel after 6 days *in vitro* [151]. Moreover, radiolabeled CAR T cells could be visualized for at least 6 days post injection in intracranially implanted glioblastoma tumors in NSG mice, without hampering CAR T cell-mediated tumor killing. V γ 9V δ 2 T cells were also radiolabeled using ^{89}Zr -oxine [152]. Radiolabeling of these $\gamma\delta$ T cells did not hamper viability and proliferation and allowed the tracking of these cells to breast cancer xenografts within 48 h.

Labeling of cell membrane proteins via chelators can also be performed, circumventing the need of disrupting the cell membrane. However, radionuclide release would still be a major concern during clinical imaging. Therefore, a novel labeling agent, called ^{89}Zr -labeled-*p*-isothiocyanato-benzyl-desferrioxamine (^{89}Zr -DBN), was developed [153]. ^{89}Zr -DBN labels lysine residues of cell surface proteins without affecting cell viability and showing no release of the tracer. Lee *et al.* recently employed this strategy to label anti-CD19-CAR expressing Jurkat T cells [154]. Although CAR T cells were efficiently radiolabeled and were detectable via PET/CT imaging, migration of the CAR T cells to the Burkitt's lymphoma tumor was not observed, likely due to the artificial nature of the Jurkat cell line.

Overall, direct labeling seems an interesting approach for the non-invasive imaging of adoptive T-cell therapies as labeling protocols are relatively easy and the target cells are already harvested from the patient for the cell therapy itself, but optimization of the imaging time window is needed.

Indirect labeling of T cells is based on the transduction of a reporter gene inside these cells [155]. A wide variety of reporter genes have been described, with the herpes simplex virus thymidine kinase (HSV-TK), being the most widely used [156,157] reporter. Some advantages of indirect labeling include the ability to inject the contrast agent at any time point, less cell toxicity and no dilution of the radioactive signal over time, since cell progeny also expresses the gene reporter. However, immunogenicity of the reporter genes, due to expression of a foreign protein at the cell surface, remains a general concern. To circumvent this problem, endogenous human reporters such as the sodium-iodide symporter (hNIS), somatostatin receptor 2 and human norepinephrine transporter (hNET) have been proposed. The sensitivity of several of these reporters to detect human T cells has been tested in athymic nude mice, with some of these reporters being able to visualize only up to 30–40.000 cells [158], leaving room for improvement. This labeling strategy has also been clinically evaluated, in recurrent high-grade glioma patients [159]. Cytotoxic T cells were engineered to express the tumor-targeting interleukin-13 zetakine and the HSV-TK reporter and were visualized using ^{18}F -FHBG in 7 patients. Administration of ^{18}F -FHBG allowed the visualization of

Fig. 3. Labeling strategies for imaging of adoptively transferred T cells. Schematic overview of ex vivo and in vivo labeling strategies to track (engineered) T cells. Ex vivo labeling approaches can be further divided in labeling of cell membranes with imaging agents or passive diffusion of imaging agents in the cell. In vivo labeling makes use of viral transduction of a reporter gene. A radiotracer/contrast agent can be introduced in the patient at a given point and will bind specifically to the expressed reporter gene. Widely used chelators, isotopes and reporter genes for the different approaches are summarized.

the CAR T cells within the tumors, showing the clinical potential of this method. Recently, prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA) was used as reporter gene to visualize anti-CD19 CAR T cells [160]. Expression of PSMA is restricted to a few organs and can be visualized with the FDA-approved PET imaging agent [^{18}F]DCFPyL [161,162,163]. Infiltration of PSMA-expressing anti-CD19 CAR T cells could be visualized in local and metastatic CD19-positive Nalm6 B-cell tumors in NSG mice. Moreover, the amount of visualized CAR T cells in the mouse tumors was similar to the amount found in human biopsies from a clinical trial. Finally, no correlation between CAR T cell tumor infiltration, as seen via PET imaging, and the amount of CAR T cells present in peripheral blood, which is current clinical practice, was observed. This suggests that more clinically relevant information could be obtained via PET imaging instead of analyzing peripheral blood. As indirect labeling allows for imaging of the engineered T cells at any time point after administration, it will provide invaluable information about the dynamics of these T cells in patients.

9. Perspectives

The non-invasive imaging of TAMs and tumor-infiltrating T cells clearly holds great promise to optimize cancer therapy regimens. One caveat to solve is the specificity of the markers to be targeted, which should be as specific as possible for the cell type of interest, and ideally even more specific for tumor-infiltrating cells as compared to their peripheral counterparts to minimize antigen sinks. In the case of macrophages, no such marker has been found up to now. While markers such as CD206 and SIRP α have proven their use for both imaging and therapy, they are not unique to TAM and need to deal with peripheral side effects. Other markers such as MARCO [159], CD204[160] and CD163[161] have been shown useful for therapy, but still need to be assessed in imaging, and their expression has been reported on macrophages in various tissues as well. The same remark holds true for (activated) T cells. Perhaps a notable exception are tumor-infiltrating regulatory T cells (Tregs), for which the chemokine receptor CCR8 was reported as

a relatively specific marker. Anti-CCR8 Nbs effectively eliminate highly suppressive Tregs from the TME, but do not affect peripheral Tregs, as such safeguarding self tolerance [162]. Current progress in single cell technologies, including CITE-sequencing that provides transcriptomic as well as surface proteomic information, has already uncovered multiple TAM subsets in various tumor types [65,163] and may yield markers that are more TAM-specific. The same holds true for tumor-infiltrating T cells.

Another future perspective is the imaging of other immunoregulatory myeloid cells in the TME. Indeed, also neutrophils or granulocytic MDSC are important contributors to immunoregulation in tumors [164,165] and could have an added value when it comes to establishing a complete view on T-cell-regulating myeloid cells. Unfortunately, no imaging nor therapeutic biologics are currently in use to assess the presence and activity of these cells. The same holds true for eosinophils, which can also play a role in anti-tumor immunity [166].

Besides biological challenges, there are also some technical and translational hurdles to overcome during a biologics-aided therapeutic approach. Ideally, the targeting agent is widely available and produced in an easy and cost-effective manner. Moreover, the tracer should accumulate rapidly, and as specifically as possible, in the TME, allowing fast imaging (in the case of nuclear imaging) and minimizing off target toxicity and radiation exposure [164]. Currently, mAbs are mostly used as targeting agents, but they have some unfavorable characteristics for a theranostic approach, as discussed in the Introduction. The combination of the high production costs of mAbs, and the inability of using short-lived isotopes and performing same-day imaging after tracer injection (due to the long circulation time of mAbs), may limit the broad applicability of mAbs as theranostics. Smaller biologics, such as minibodies, cys-diabodies and nanobodies may solve (most of) these problems. However, the full potential of these smaller formats still needs to be proven, since only few of them are currently being tested clinically. Moreover, further developments in T-cell engineering and production for adoptive T-cell therapy will be essential to lower the overall cost price of this immunotherapy.

This could also be beneficial for the further clinical development of T-cell molecular imaging.

The end goal of using diagnostic and/or therapeutic biologics is to provide a personalized immune-oncology medicine approach. However, the (future) integration of these theranostics in clinical practice remains challenging or unclear. Given the complexity and interpatient heterogeneity of the TME, it is unlikely that one tracer will be sufficient to monitor and/or predict treatment responsiveness. Hence, a combination of tracers could provide a broader overview of a patient's immune status, but will be challenging to implement in an efficient, cost-effective and patient-friendly manner in clinical practice. Nevertheless, it will be important to outweigh costs and benefits, as this approach could improve patients' outcomes, reduce adverse toxicity and diminish overall healthcare costs by avoiding inefficient therapies. Moreover, immuno-imaging with these tracers could aid in reducing the amount of false positive/negative cases when performing ^{18}F -FDG PET/CT. To date, a wrong interpretation of ^{18}F -FDG PET/CT scans can be due to a variety of causes, including incorrect patient preparation, sites with higher physiological FDG uptake (e.g. brain, liver, spleen), infections, treatment-related conditions (e.g. pseudoprogression, inflammation) or FDG-PET negative tumors [165]. Immuno-imaging could provide additional information and possibly resolve some of these issues. However, the interpretation of immuno-imaging results (infiltration of T cells in the TME vs T-cell distribution within the TME, intratumoral CAR-T cells vs peripheral blood CAR-T cells) and its correlation with therapy outcome should be investigated further.

Altogether, the field of immune imaging is still expanding and new tracer formulations, as well as new molecular targets are expected to further refine our insights in the biodistribution and functional kinetics of tumor-infiltrating immune cells.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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